

RECYCLING OF HIGH PERFORMANCE THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES WITH HIGH VOLTAGE FRAGMENTATION

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1 Abstract

The recycling from advanced composites structures has so far been focussing on energy recovery or recovery of ground fibres via a pyrolysis process. This paper describes the recovering of fibres with their thermoplastics matrix through a novel process referred to as high voltage fragmentation or electro-dynamical fragmentation. It could be demonstrated that a cradle-to-cradle re-use of composite materials is possible without significant loss in properties, based on complex structural components made from chopped thermoplastic composite tapes.

2 Introduction

Carbon fibre reinforced polymers (CFRPs) are most widely used in the aerospace industry for the production of large components and contributes to the fuel efficiency of the new generation aircrafts. However the end-of-life of such materials represents a major challenge to this industry. European legislation assigns the responsibility for disposing of end-of-life materials [1] to the manufacturer. Their current approach is to landfill the components or dispose the retired aircrafts in desert graveyards [2]. Currently over 2000 aircrafts reside in such graveyards and over 5000 commercial airliners are to be expected to be withdrawn from service over the next 20 years [3].

2.1 Recycling approaches for end-of-life of CFRP components

It has been shown that the main energy in most manufacturing scenarios is actually attributed to the manufacturing of the carbon fibre itself [4]. It is therefore the most valuable constituent to recover. One recycling solution is to remove the thermosetting matrix from the carbon fibres by thermal pyrolysis. New methods are being developed in order to increase the quality of the

recovered carbon fibres by critical water oxidation or micro-wave pyrolysis [5]. The recovery of the thermoset matrix is much more difficult as the cross-link reaction of epoxy resins and amine hardeners is generally considered as a non-reversible reaction leading to an infinite network of covalent bonds. In contrast to thermoset composites, carbon fibre reinforced *thermoplastic* polymers have an inherent potential for recycling by re-melting and hence re-processing the matrix [6]. Thermoplastics matrix systems such PEEK (polyetheretherketone), PES (polyethersulfone) or PPS (polyphenylenesulfide) exhibit mechanical properties close to the best thermoset polymers. The authors have developed processes based on thermoplastic CFRP tapes to compression mould complex load bearing parts [7]. Such parts have the potential to replace complex metallic fittings.

2.1 High voltage fragmentation

One novel approach to separate a composite into its constituents is *high voltage fragmentation* (Fig. 2), also referred to as *electro-dynamical fragmentation* in literature. The method was already investigated in the 1960s at Tomsk Polytechnic Institute in Russia [8] and has found applications in mining to separate and extract crystals from rocks. This is achieved by electrical discharges through or near the specimen to be decomposed. The (usually brittle) materials are placed in water between electrodes; high voltage pulses, typically between 100 to 200 kV, are applied. The voltage has to be higher than the actual breakdown voltage of the material to be fragmented, but lower than the surrounding water. This is achieved by keeping the pulse time below 5 μ s (Fig. 1). The temperature along the plasma channel in the discharge will rise up to 10000°C and will evaporate material to a certain extend along its path; the main fracturing mechanism is however attributed to the high pressure peak of up to 10⁴ MPa occurring

along the discharge channel. This value being larger than the strength of most materials, the resulting shock wave will lead to a fracturing of surrounding materials.

The physics of fragmentation and hence separation of different constituents is based on several mechanisms: In the case of inclusions with higher permittivity, the electrical discharge will be attracted to follow the boundary separating the inclusion from the rest. Furthermore, material inhomogeneities also lead to stress concentration on its boundaries, which attracts the crack tip during fragmentation. Cracks propagated from a discharge can branch around an inclusion especially when the mechanical properties differ from the surrounding material.

This method is finding increasing interest in recycling and recovery of rare earth metals in urban electronic waste [8], however little is known on application on composites, mainly being limited to trials on electric circuit boards [9], as they represented one of the early high volume markets for composites materials. The separation of polymer based materials systems is more challenging particularly if their fracture toughness is very high. In the case of rubber systems liquid nitrogen has been used to lower the temperature below its glass transition point to reduce the fracture toughness [10], the success was however limited due to the low electric breakdown strength of liquid nitrogen.

Fig. 1 Breakdown field strength from rock and water in function of voltage rise time, above 500 ns, water has a lower value than the rock, (from[8]modified).

In the context of this work, this method has been applied for recycling carbon fibre reinforced thermoplastic polymers. In spite of the high

toughness of these matrix systems, the presence of fibres and resulting high orthotropy might nevertheless be beneficial for a fragmentation.

Fig. 2 Principle of high voltage fragmentation. The material immersed in water. The discharge pulses pass through or near the material

3 Materials and Methods

3.1 Load introductions made from thermoplastics composites based on chopped tapes

Typical metallic load introduction in CFRP structures have drawbacks: Aluminium has to be protected from galvanic corrosion from carbon fibres through cost intensive precautions. Titanium is not subjected to galvanic corrosion but is very costly as a raw material and expensive to machine. Last but not least steel is penalised by its high density. So far the use of CFRPs for load introductions has been limited because it is very difficult to represent complex geometries based on the common fibre alignment and layered structure associated to woven respectively non-crimp fabrics.

We have addressed this problem by developing a net shape manufacturing process for complex load introductions for thermoplastic composites based on chopped tapes. One component used for demonstration in the scope of this study was a rotorcraft door hinge from a well-known civil twin engine helicopter, which was redesigned for this new process. The base materials used in this process was unidirectional tape (supplied by Suprem SA) made of AS4 carbon fibre in a PEEK matrix at a fibre volume content of 55%. This tape was chopped to 10 respectively 20mm length.

The manufacturing process consists of the following steps. The chopped tapes are filled into the cavity by gravimetric dosing; the mould is inserted into a press

with a variothermal heating and cooling unit. The cavity is heated above the melt temperature of the polymer (approximately 380°C for PEEK) while an equivalent cavity pressure between 50 to 150 bar is applied. After a consolidation phase the mould is cooled to demoulding temperature. The overall cycle time is about 40 min at laboratory scale. The effects of chips size effect and processing conditions was investigated in detail by the authors [11]. By exploiting the specific properties of the CFRP as well as benefiting from an added design freedom, a weight reduction of 80% was achieved compared to the original steel hinge.

Fig. 3 Compression mould cavity for the CFRP rotorcraft door hinge.

3.2 High Voltage fragmentation process

The specimens were subsequently recycled with the use of a high voltage fragmentation lab unit by Selfrag AG. The fragmentation is operated by putting the specimen in a closed vessel using 3 to 4 litres of water. Fragmentation carried out with 150-

Fig. 6 From left to right: Effects of fragmentation on the thermoplastic CFRP with increasing number of pulses.

200 pulses. The fragments were ordered in size fractions by filtration and separated from residues. Large fragments were re-submitted to fragmentation. The operation was repeated until the yield of fragments in the desired size was maximized (Fig. 6).

Fig. 4 Compression moulded CFRP rotorcraft door hinge.

These fragments (Fig. 5) were subsequently reprocessed to new parts with the identical variothermal compression moulding process described above.

Fig. 5 Left: virgin chips. Right: chips resulting from high voltage fragmentation

3.3 Characterization of recycled products

A scanning electron microscope (SEM) was used in this study in order to visualize fracture surfaces and the composite tapes before and after recycling.

The CFRP hinges were tested in a specific support (Fig. 7) using the 4 mounting holes, the force and displacement were recorded.

Fig. 7 Testing configuration of the rotorcraft door hinges. The proof load was 2172 N.

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Fragmentation process

The electrodynamic fragmentation was carried out in a batch process with short cycles to remove powder and small particles. This is due to the fact that fragmentation speed increases with smaller fragment

size due to the increased specific surface (for discharge attack) which would lead to very uneven fragment size distribution. This processing aspect would be solved with continuous sieving in an industrial setup. The different fragment size fraction were therefore treated individually to give a size distribution close to the original chips.

The specific phases of the fragmentation process are shown in Fig. 9: The parts are first attacked on the edges mainly due to field enhancement effects, referred to as the weakening phase. After some surface defects are present, discharge will go through the part leading to delamination the delamination phase, the associated increase in surface then leads to the actual fragmentation phase with the maximum yield. As correct size fragments are removed by sieving, the yield is reduced in the final ending phase, where remaining larger fragments are quickly reduced.

It could be expected that fragmentation would reconstitute the actual chips geometry. This is not the case. The interlaminar adhesion between layers is so strong that the fragmentation process also leads to some extent of failure next to the expected delamination. The resulting fragments are therefore

Fig. 8 SEM picture of a fragment after electrodynamic fragmentation (a), Fragment surfaces with fibre still covered with thermoplastic polymer (b) and with very clean fibres free of polymer (c)

smaller than the original chips and are typical composed from several through thickness chips layers and therefore have a different aspect ratio compared to the original chips (Fig. 6).

The analysis of the fragment in SEM (Fig. 8) nevertheless showed that many fibres have maintained their original length (a). Some areas showed small residues of polymer remaining after fracture (b), while other showed clean fibres without any polymer (c). The latter is possibly associated to the high local temperatures from the discharge.

Composite fragmentation

Fig. 9 The principal phases of the fragmentation yield versus the number of pulses applied to the part. (A) weakening, (B) delamination, (C) fragmentation and (D) ending.

A direct comparison from fragment to virgin types as shown on Fig. 11 and Fig. 10 suggests that polymer is removed from the fragment surface

independently from the physics of the fragmentation, as fibre surface becomes visible in spite of the polymer residues present.

4.2 Compression moulding hinges from recycled fragments

The recycled fragments were selected by sieving a fraction with dimensional range from 0.5 to 4 mm. The manufacturing from hinges was executed with the same processing parameters as the virgin parts: The cavity was heated above the melt temperature of the polymer (approximately 380°C) while an equivalent cavity pressure between 50 to 150 bar is applied. After a consolidation phase the mould was cooled to de-moulding temperature. The overall cycle time was about 40 min. The exterior aspect of the hinges was similar than the parts made from virgin tapes.

4.3 Mechanical testing of hinges made from recycled fragments

The load bearing test on the demonstrator revealed that the mechanical properties of the door hinges made with recycled thermoplastic composites were comparable to the ones made with virgin chopped tapes (Fig. 14). The strength of the recycled door hinges reached about 80% of those made from virgin chopped tapes.

The decrease of mechanical properties in the recycled part is attributed to two effects i) chips coming from fragmentation are shorter than the original ones, ii) moreover, the discharge led to a removal of the polymer at the surface of a fragment

Fig. 11 Virgin tapes where carbon fibres are entirely covered with polymer matrix

Fig. 10 After fragmentation, polymer is removed from the fibres lying on the outer surface of the fragment.

(Fig. 13 and Fig. 12). This fact correlated to the observation made on the fragment previous to processing. The reduction of polymer content on the fragmented and reprocessed part was confirmed by measuring a slightly higher fibre volume content. This explains in a decrease of adhesion between fragments in the final part.

5 Conclusion

It could be demonstrated that high voltage fragmentation is a suitable method for recycling high performance carbon fibre reinforced thermoplastic polymers, offering the potential of reuse of materials from cradle to cradle. Fragments can be reprocessed to parts with limited loss in properties. These origin losses could attribute to the reduction of polymer content on the fragment surface. Future work will address the detrimental effects of the reduction of

polymer content on the surface of the fragment and will aim on transforming the batch fragmentation process to a continuous process.

Thermoplastics composites have previously been identified as good candidates for replacing metallic parts in aerospace applications. The perspective to recycle such materials cradle to cradle offers a new potential for such materials under life cycle considerations.

Fig. 12 Fracture of the original door hinge: Photo of the hinge bearing area (a), SEM picture of the fracture (b) and of aligned fibres with a chopped tape arrangement well embedded in polymer (c).

Fig. 13 Fracture of the recycled door hinge: SEM picture of the fracture (a), area with randomly oriented fibres with poor polymer/fibre adhesion (b), overall view (c) and high magnification (d) of area with aligned fibres.

Fig. 14 Bearing load from hinges made from recycled and from virgin tapes of different size.

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